

LABORATORY PRACTICES FOR PURIFICATION OF DRINKING WATER

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Cyanophytes encompass an old subdivision of minuscule organisms, settled in a large variety of environments such as freshwaters, sea, oceans, rocks, soil and hot springs. In freshwaters, some are benthic, but many are found on the surface, floating at the mercy of winds and water currents. Under enriched conditions, these unicellular microscopic entities multiply profusely, amassed together and form scums. On lysis, they produce toxins that are not easily inactivated by laboratory equivalents of water purification process viz. flocculation-filtration-chlorination treatment. Even activated carbon, in small doses, falls short to yield desirable results. However, vast amount of charcoal can do so. Besides, activated carbon filtration, in combination with ionization, has been found effectual in neutralizing toxins.

As a rule, slow sand-filters are considered to be more dependable than high-speed filters in doing away with phytoplankton. *Albeit*, the slow filters do not take out color from water as some cyanophytes succeed in penetrating the filtration bed. Moreover, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, at the ultimate stages of bloom formation secretes substantial amount of organic compounds with polysaccharide base. This dross is seldom removed by conventional treatments like sand-filtration, $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ coagulation, $FeCl_3$ flocculation, sedimentation, etc. and much of it goes into the water supply, making the water obnoxious to users. Though toxic degradations are possible, yet the current state of practice seems insufficient to exterminate cent-per-cent algae from raw water entering the supply system.

Although there is no way to deal with these nuisance microphytes, use of blue stone CuSO_4 in chunk or granular form can be suggested as an algicide. However, the same cannot be used further than a certain limit and that too in a large basin. Obviously, ionization at the end of filtration may be a good permutation to get rid of plant organisms with their associated organoleptic properties.

Key words : Coagulation, Filtration, Flocculation, Sedimentation, Toxicity.

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